

Non-canonical internalization mechanisms of mGlu receptors

LIST OF OBJECTS

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Object#01: DERET revealed internalization properties of ST-mGlu5

Object#02: Kinetic analysis reveals different internalization profiles of mGlu homodimers

Object#03: Different recycling properties of internalized ST-mGlu5 and ST-mGlu3 receptors

Object#04: Only ST-mGlu2-3 among the ST-mGlu3-containing heterodimers internalizes upon agonist stimulation

Object#05: GRKs are not mandatory for mGlu receptor internalization

Object#06: GRKs fine tune mGlu receptor internalization

Object#07: β arrs are required for constitutive mGlu receptor internalization

Object#08: C-terminal domain of ST-mGlu3 is involved in the constitutive association with β arr

Object#09: AP2 is required for agonist-induced internalization of mGlu receptors

Object#10: Control of receptor expression

Object#11: Internalization kinetics of mGlu receptors

Object#12: GRK impact on mGlu internalization

Object#13: Impact of GRKs and β arr in Group-I mGlu receptor internalization kinetics

Object#14: Impact of β arr in mGlu receptor internalization kinetics

Object#15: Controls for β arr recruitment

Object#16: Chimeras internalization kinetics

Object#17: Controls for AP2 internalization experiments

Object#18: Downregulation of μ AP2 subunit effect on internalization in control cells and cell with downregulated AP2

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